

Optimizing Energy Efficiency in Optical Transport Networks through Autonomous AI-Assisted Control Operations

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Abstract: This work explores Deep Reinforcement Learning to develop advanced RMSA policies that support autonomous control operations, optimizing the trade-off between network performance and energy efficiency in integrated packet and elastic optical networks.

1. Introduction

Network operators view integrating packet nodes (routers) with compact, pluggable coherent DWDM transceivers (e.g., 400/800ZR+) and elastic optical networks (EON) as crucial for managing broadband growth [1]. This transport infrastructure reduces network complexity by eliminating standalone DWDM transponders, improving both CapEx and power efficiency. Sustainability is now a key goal, pushing operators to balance power consumption and data throughput (W/Gb/s) for better energy efficiency [2]. This can be achieved by deploying greener technologies, such as DWDM *pluggables*, and using advanced energy-aware routing and traffic engineering strategies [3].

Optical Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controllers are increasingly incorporating autonomic control functions to manage optical connectivity services. These include Routing, Modulation and Spectrum Assignment (RMSA) algorithms, telemetry systems, and programmable device APIs (e.g., NETCONF, OpenConfig, OpenROADM). To address sustainability goals, SDN operations must prioritize energy-efficient decisions that balance network throughput and power consumption. In this context, energy-aware RMSA (EA-RMSA) strategies enhance traditional RSMA by computing paths, spectral resources, and transceiver configurations, such as Operational Modes (OMs) defined by symbol rates and modulation formats, to improve energy efficiency. EA-RMSA not only meets service demands (e.g., bandwidth) while adhering to EON constraints (spectrum continuity and contiguity) but also minimizes the activation of power-consuming devices such as ROADMs, amplifiers, transceivers, etc. Traditionally handled by heuristic RMSA algorithms [3], this complex task now benefits from AI/ML approaches like Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) [4]. We propose a DRL-based EA-RMSA model designed to achieve superior energy efficiency (kW/Gb/s) than widely adopted RSMA strategies, such as K-Shortest Path routing with First-Fit spectrum assignment (KSP-FF) and its energy-aware enhancement (EA-KSP-FF) [3][4]. Its performance is evaluated under various traffic loads with diverse bandwidth demands, using metrics such as Blocked Bandwidth Ratio (BBR), average energy efficiency, power consumption per device (ROADMs, links, transceivers, etc.), and average transceiver utilization.

2. Power Consumption Model

Figure 1(a) depicts the power consumption calculation for provisioning a connection along the path R1-ROADM1-ROADM2-ROADM3-R2. To satisfy the requested bandwidth (b/s), the RMSA algorithm determines the required number of DWDM coherent transceivers, m , at both R1 and R2. Coherent transceivers support various operational modes (OMs), as shown in Fig. 1(b), offering different bit rates and maximum path distances based on the aggregated link length. For each candidate OM that satisfies the path distance constraint, the RMSA algorithm outputs m transceivers (configured to the selected OM) at R1 and R2, along with m optical flows specifying central frequencies and slot widths to be allocated along the path.

Router power consumption (P_{R_i}) with m configured transceivers is given in Eq. 1 [1], where P_{idle}^{router} denotes idle power (router on, no traffic) and P_{OM}^{cvt} represents power consumption for a specific OM. As shown in Fig. 1(b), higher OMs, with complex modulation formats, increase power dissipation in components like the ADC, DAC, and DSP, as higher data rates require more intensive signal processing. Power consumption from Optical Line Amplifiers (OLAs) along fiber links is denoted by $P_{link_{i,j}}$, in Eq. 2. Active ROADMs' power (Eq. 3) includes: i) idle power (P_{idle}^{ROADM}) caused by fans, control system, etc.; and ii) power from active optical ports (e.g., WSSs, amplifiers, mux/demux) for adjacent ROADM connections. Roughly, idle power of active devices (routers, ROADMs) consumes 70-75% of the total network power. If a device (i.e., router, ROADM, port, or link) is already powered by an existing service, adding a new service does not increase power. Eq. 4 calculates the total power for those devices activated along a connection.

3. Considered Energy-Aware RMSA algorithms: Heuristics and DRL-based

A service request, R , is defined as the tuple (s, d, b) , where s and d are the source and destination routers, and b is the bitrate (b/s). When a new R is received, the RMSA algorithm searches for a feasible path and selects an OM to meet R 's bitrate. The algorithm also determines the necessary m optical flows/transceivers for the chosen OM, specifying central frequencies and slot widths. A common KSP-FF algorithm prioritizes the most advanced OMs and computes K paths to minimize hop count while ensuring that all required carriers meet end-to-end optical continuity and contiguity constraints. EA-KSP-FF extends KSP-FF to further minimize network power consumption by computing power increases for each k -path using above power model. Feasible K paths are sorted by power consumption and hops, with EA-KSP-FF favoring paths through already active devices to avoid powering on new elements [4]. To enhance the balance between network performance (e.g., BBR) and energy efficiency, we propose an offline-trained DRL model, DRL EA-KSP. The DRL agent, employing a Deep Neural Network (DNN), learns optimal decisions by interacting with the network environment, including packet and EON topology, optical spectrum, transceivers, and dynamic requests R . For each R , the *observation* (as shown in Fig. 1(c)) includes two one-hot arrays for the source and destination nodes and a set of $OM * K$ candidate paths. Each path is characterized by spectrum attributes [4], requested spectrum, and a vector indicating specific EON links across the k -path. The *action* space covers all feasible paths, up to $OM * K$. The reward function (Eq. 5) incentivizes actions that 1) increase network throughput via R 's bitrate, and 2) minimize additional power consumption ($powerPath$) for a chosen path. If no feasible action exists (e.g., due to lack of available transceivers or EON resources), the reward is set to -1.

Fig. 1. (a) Power consumption model for integrated packet nodes with 400G ZR+ pluggable and EON infrastructure; (b) Considered power consumption parameters; (c) DRL EA-RMSA: observation space and reward; (d) Transport topology.

4. Performance Evaluation

To train the DRL EA-KSP model, a maskable *Proximal Policy Optimization* (PPO) is employed, with 3 fully connected hidden layers of 128 neurons each, a learning rate of 10^{-5} , and a discount factor of 0.95. Training spans 1000 episodes, each generating 20000 R s requests via a Poisson process with a 50s inter-arrival time. The R s' duration follows an exponential distribution, with Holding Time (HT) ranging from 2000 to 3500s. The requested bitrate (b) is randomly selected from [100, 200, 300, 400] Gb/s. The network topology, shown in Fig. 2(d), comprises 44 bidirectional optical links with specified distances, determining the placement of Optical Line Amplifiers (OLAs) spaced 80 km apart. Network links support optical spectrum from 191.3 to 196.1 THz, i.e., 768 Nominal Central Frequencies (NCFs) spaced at 6.25 GHz. Each optical flow setting up R , regardless of the selected OM, occupies 50 GHz. Finally, each router connects to the EON via 15 coherent DWDM transceivers (pluggable).

Fig. 2(a) shows the BBR achieved by the adopted RMSA strategies: KSP-FF, EA-KSP-FF, and DRL EA-KSP. As expected, the KSP-FF algorithm attains the lowest (best) BBR across all traffic loads by prioritizing spectral resource

utilization to accommodate as many requests (R) as possible, regardless of network power consumption. However, tackling network sustainability requires balancing the attained BBR with energy efficiency, measured as the average network power consumption (kW) per served throughput (Gb/s). The lower this metric, the more power-efficient the RMSA strategy. As shown in Fig. 2(b), EA-KSP-FF improves KSP-FF energy efficiency by 7.6% to 8.8%, depending on the traffic load. This gain arises from EA-KSP-FF accommodating requests (R s) through already active ROADMs and links (i.e., reusing OLAs). Thus, average network power consumption decreases by 7.6% to 9.8% compared to KSP-FF. Fig. 2(d) shows this improvement is consistently tied to reduced power consumption in both ROADMs and optical links, regardless of traffic load. Notably, both KSP-FF and EA-KSP-FF achieve similar average transceiver utilization (see Fig. 2(c)) with minor differences in the utilized OMs, being OM#3 (DP-8QAM) the most used. The primary goal of the DRL EA-KSP solution is to enhance the energy efficiency achieved by EA-KSP-FF. As shown in Fig. 2(b), this improvement ranges from 3.2% to 6.6%, driven by more efficient utilization of active ROADMs and optical links, along with optimized selection of transceivers' OMs, reducing device power consumption. Notably, DRL EA-KSP achieves the highest average transceiver utilization compared to KSP-FF and EA-KSP-FF (see Fig. 2(c)). Transceivers in DRL EA-KSP are configured with the lowest-power OMs, specifically OM#1 and OM#2 tied to DP-QPSK for 30 and 60 Gbaud rates, respectively, with usage rates between 76% and 79%. In contrast, EA-KSP-FF achieves only around 30% utilization of these low-power OMs. While DRL EA-KSP improves energy efficiency, it slightly degrades BBR performance, as observed in Fig. 2(a), emphasizing the trade-off between network performance (BBR) and energy efficiency (kW/Gb/s).

Fig. 2: (a) BBR; (b) Energy Efficiency (kW/Gb/s); (c) Average transceiver & Operational Modes utilization (%); (d) Power consumption (%) per network devices

5. Conclusions

In SDN-controlled transport networks with coherent transceivers and EON, functions like RMSA computation must evolve to prioritize sustainability and energy efficiency. This requires modeling the power consumption of key components, including transceivers, ROADMs, routers, and optical links. We propose a DRL-based RMSA strategy that outperforms traditional heuristics, such as (EA-)KSP-FF, in energy efficiency. Results show that DRL EA-KSP adapts more effectively to network conditions, achieving a better balance between BBR and energy efficiency.

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